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THE TRAINING OF SPECIALISTS IN THE FIELD OF PHYSICS AND ITS AGRARIAN SECTOR IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: The article highlights the following sections of Physics, Mechanics, molecular physics, electrodynamics, optics, atomic and nuclear physics teaching methods in the study of topics related to agriculture. The formation and development of which they can apply their theoretical knowledge in practice, independent contract various physical experiments and correct perform the analysis of the results analyzed is widely described in the article.

Key words: agricultural industry, physics, field field enhancement, livestock breeding, energy, communication, space, transportation, construction, mechanics, molecular physics, electrodynamics, optics, atomic and nuclear physics.

INTRODUCTION

The science of physics is so closely and multifaceted connected with disciplines related to the field of Agriculture that physics is obliged to have an indisputable place in measures to increase field yields and increase livestock production [1].

Physics is a science of nature and the technical school has a special place among the disciplines of the curriculum. It forms a scientific picture of being in the minds of listeners, shows them the humanistic nature of scientific knowledge, draws attention to its specific moral significance, forms creative abilities in listeners, their worldview, systematic views on being, since the Earth is an open system, and man is considered a branch of nature.

At the expense of the achievements of Physical Science, Energy, communication, space, transport, construction, industrial and agricultural production will develop in interconnection.

Neither only at the present stage of the development of our state, but also the development of all world countries, problems in the field of agriculture are of particular interest and are considered very relevant.

The main content and essence of the decisions and decrees adopted by our state and president in the field of Agriculture is the modernization of the agrarian sector and the transition to an innovative model of Industry Development, digitalization of the agrarian sector and strengthening food security by creating advanced innovative technologies. This in turn makes our state lose its

dependence on other countries and ultimately elevates the authority of our state among the world's states to higher ones.

The following sections of physics occupy a special place in the study of topics related to the agricultural sector: mechanics, molecular physics, electrodynamics, optics, atomic and nuclear physics. They help the audience acquire and form and develop the following knowledge and skills:

* principles of operation of agricultural machines, their capacity and energy supply;

• to control and account for temperature and humidity, their importance in agricultural production;

* the physical basis of drying and moisture formation, irrigation and other reclamation activities;

• information on mechanization and automation of Agriculture, digitalization of agriculture based on the application of the laws of physics;

* economical and efficient use of electricity in livestock, poultry and greenhouse farms;

* prospects for digitalization and electrification of Agriculture;

• use of scientific achievements in the field of atomic and nuclear physics in Agriculture, Livestock, Poultry, Fisheries and other fields [2-14].

RESULTS

The study and assimilation of the issues and problems listed above plays a special role in finding solutions to the following issues

Firstly, when studying each section of physics, it is necessary to select the most important from within the directions of scientific and technical progression, and secondly, after studying the generalized topic at the end of each section of physics, students create conditions for eliminating the uzuk - yuluk points formed in the corresponding section in the process of obtaining knowledge and isolating only the necessary

In the fifth level of Education (Technical Schools), the importance of physical science is determined by the role of Physical Science in the life of modern society. The achievements of physical science are very widely used in agricultural production. In vast fields, various tractors and units, cars work, that is, complex automation, mechanization and digitization of Agriculture make people out of hard manual labor.

Living in the countryside also has its own aspects, and the application of physical laws in goal-oriented practice, as well as understanding the essence, were their long-standing dreams, and they act on such work from childhood. In addition, in

later times, farms and clusters were established in each village, and rural youth actively participate in their lives, since the parents of most of them operate on these farms. Ultimately, most young people have to go after their parents and communicate with tractors, aggregates and cars, as well as combines. In doing so, they will have to know the application of the laws of physics in agricultural production when it comes to increasing productivity and increasing livestock production. To do this, of course, they must first study the laws of physics and apply these laws to more complex processes, first supporting them in simple mechanisms, and then understand their performance. Of course, the role of technical schools in the acquisition of such professions is incomparable.

The development of Science and technology requires humanity to improve its knowledge and skills in the process of work. In such conditions, the role of physics, from the point of view of the fact that it is considered the basis of the technique, GOG also increases. As a result of his tireless research on himself, the trainee becomes a mature specialist in the field of Agriculture.

CONCLUSION

The adoption of decisions and decrees on agriculture by the president and the state "on measures to further improve the activities of the Tashkent State Agrarian University" is of great importance in ensuring food security, the establishment of Agricultural Technical Institutions in the agrarian sector is a decision taken in time to find solutions to existing problems.

Purpose of science:

- * In the audience, the formation of intellectual knowledge and skills;
- It consists in the study of the laws of physics and their practical and efficient use in agricultural production.

The main tasks of science:

- * Familiarization with the main methods of applying the laws of physics in agriculture;
- * Develop their interest in learning about modern agricultural techniques and environmental problems;
- * Development of creative and indeletical abilities of the audience so that they can independently acquire knowledge and develop their skills in physics;
- * Formation and development of the skills of using information technologies, including from various sources of information so that they can apply digital technologies in agricultural production;

* Formation and development of the ability to apply the knowledge gained in theory in practice, be able to independently conduct various physical experiments and correctly perform the analysis of the results obtained;

* Formation and development of mutual respect in the process of joint work, truthful assessment by hearing other people's opinions, the ability to think logically.

Expected results from teaching science:

* generate and develop perceptions of students ' ability to apply physical laws and factors in agriculture;

* develop their interest in obtaining knowledge, increasing their intellectual and creative abilities, relying on theoretical knowledge and experience, they independently acquire new knowledge, extract the necessary information from the data stream and use it correctly, and be able to evaluate them by expressing their opinion on new information;

* develop professional professional activities as having the skills to bring new knowledge without reaching the essence.

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